

Flexible and Printed Electronics

PAPER

All solution-processed ultra-thin piezoelectric films for sensing applications

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Abstract

The development of flexible electronics is essential for advancing technologies like wearables, environmental sensors, and electronic skin (e-skin), which are used in applications ranging from healthcare to soft robotics. E-skin, inspired by the human skin's sensory capabilities, requires flexible and conformable materials to mimic the dynamic responses to shear, pressure, temperature, and pain. Traditional rigid electronics fabrication methods, which require high processing temperatures, are unsuitable for flexible substrates. Additionally, the requirement for low-power and energy-autonomous devices present challenges that could be addressed with piezoelectric materials. In this study, we present an all-solution processed method to fabricate an ultra-thin, piezoelectric sensor on a flexible polyimide substrate. The sensor's electrodes are inkjet-printed using poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate, while the active layer of poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-trifluoroethylene) is formed by spin coating. The fabrication process is optimized by varying annealing temperatures and using two casting solvents while spin coating, methyl ethyl ketone and dimethyl sulfoxide, to assess their impact on the active layer performance. The resulting sensor has a sandwiched structure with a final thickness of less than 1 μm , including a 289 nm thick active layer. The sensor demonstrates a remanent polarization P_r of 7.9 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ and a piezoelectric coefficient d_{33} of 12.4 pC N^{-1} .

1. Introduction

The development of fabrication methods for flexible electronics is crucial in advancing technologies such as wearables, environmental sensors, and electronic skin (e-skin), which are widely used in applications ranging from healthcare monitoring to soft robotics [1, 2]. Electronic skin is inspired by human skin and its tremendous capabilities to sense, process, and react to shear, pressure, temperature, and pain [3]. However, the mimicry of human skin's sensory capabilities via electronics requires flexibility and conformability, posing some challenges during fabrication. The main disadvantage of traditional microfabrication methods for rigid electronics is their requirement for high processing temperatures often unsuitable for flexible substrates [4]. Moreover, to avoid wiring or bulky batteries which limit the user comfort, the next generation e-skins need to be energy-autonomous. For this purpose, the piezoelectric effect offers a promising solution for low-energy operation.

Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-trifluoroethylene) P(VDF-TrFE) is widely recognized ferroelectric copolymer used in piezoelectric sensors due to its excellent features such as flexibility, workability, and fast dynamic response [5, 6]. Numerous studies show that its unique features can be exploited widely in electronics and biotechnology applications such as energy harvesting, tactile sensing, and MEMS [7–10]. Moreover, P(VDF-TrFE)'s solution processability enables cost effective fabrication routes with low material waste and low processing temperatures making it suitable for flexible electronics [11, 12].

P(VDF-TrFE) may crystallize from the melt or from solution into two phases, the paraelectric or ferroelectric. The latter one, also called β -phase, has a structured chain conformation with all fluorine atoms pointing in the same direction (all trans TTT), resulting in strong electric dipoles. This property of β -phase in P(VDF-TrFE) results in spontaneous polarization in the material [13, 14] therefore making the ferroelectric β -phase the primary target in

Table 1. Comparison of piezoelectric properties of solution-processed P(VDF-TrFE) layers (under 5 μm) in the literature.

Fabrication method of P(VDF-TrFE) layer	Fabrication method of electrodes, electrode material	Thickness of P(VDF-TrFE) layer [nm]	Piezoelectric coefficient (d_{33})	Remanent polarization [$\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$]	reference
Spin coating	Inkjet printing, PEDOT:PSS	289^a	12.4 pC N⁻¹	7.9	This work
Inkjet printing	Inkjet printing, PEDOT:PSS	1000	N/A	N/A	[26]
Spin coating	Spin coating, PEDOT:PSS	20	17.14 pm V ⁻¹	N/A	[18]
Spin coating	Evaporation, aluminum	N/A	N/A	1.7	[19]
Spin coating	—	200	N/A	6.8	[20]
Spin coating	Evaporation, gold	70–100	0.5–1.19 pm V ⁻¹	~6 (defined from a graph)	[21]
Spin coating	Physical vapor deposition, gold	220	N/A	7	[22]
Spin coating	—	252–953	N/A	N/A	[23]
Screen printing	Screen printing, metal	3000	N/A	N/A	[25]
Spin coating	Evaporation, silver	3000	11.7 pC N ⁻¹	5.6	[24]

^a Average value from different characterization methods of sample set C.

fabrication of piezoelectric sensors. Nevertheless, despite the desired chain conformation of β -phase in P(VDF-TrFE), the net polarization of the bulk material may still be zero, as the dipoles in the semicrystalline regions are often randomly oriented. This leads to mutual cancellation of polarization in the absence of external alignment processes. To induce the net polarization of P(VDF-TrFE) thin films, the crystal domains are aligned in a so-called poling step as an external electric field higher than the coercive field E_C is applied across the film [15]. After poling, a mechanical deformation will cause a change in the net polarization proportional to the applied force. To achieve β -phase, the fabrication temperature should be above Curie temperature range while still staying below the melting temperature [16].

Achieving a uniform and thin layer of P(VDF-TrFE) through spin-coating method is straightforward, inexpensive, and suitable for solution-processed fabrication in room temperature [17] owing to the spin-coating equipment. Indeed, many studies have demonstrated fabrication of thin P(VDF-TrFE) layers by spin coating [18–24], but also by screen printing [25] and inkjet printing [26] (see table 1). In [26], inkjet printing was also employed for the fabrication of electrodes; however, key performance metrics such as the piezoelectric coefficient (d_{33}) and remanent polarization were not reported. Notably, [18] employed spin coating for both the active layer and the electrodes, and reported an ultrathin active layer thickness of approximately 20 nm. However, remanent polarization data were

not provided in that study either. Nevertheless, frequently evaporation is employed in electrode fabrication thereby limiting applications in flexible electronics and involving higher material cost.

When casting P(VDF-TrFE) thin films, water condensation from air has been shown to cause vapor induced phase separation (VIPS) into the drying solvent. Typically, VIPS is introduced in the structure deliberately to produce porous P(VDF-TrFE) structures [27, 28]. However, since VIPS heavily affects microstructure formation through causing shrinkage in domain size, its occurrence compromises the smoothness of the thin film [29]. In particular, VIPS is more likely to occur when the casting solvent has a slow evaporation rate [30]. Therefore, choosing a solvent with high evaporation rate and low hygroscopy will help to avoid ambient water causing separation in the material [29].

The present research demonstrates a simple, fast, and cost-effective route to fabricate an all-solution-processed, ultrathin piezoelectric sensor on a flexible polyimide substrate. Sensor electrodes are inkjet printed poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS), and the active layer of poly(vinylidene fluoride-trifluoroethylene) (P(VDF-TrFE)) is formed by spin coating. To optimize the fabrication process, the variability in annealing temperatures during the fabrication of the active layer is studied. In addition, two casting solvents, methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) are used to explore their effect on the formation of the active layer. To find the best possible

fabrication route, optimization was based on electrical and material characterizations. We analyzed ferroelectric P-E hysteresis loops—an established method for assessing piezoelectric thin films [31]. Sensor sensitivity was evaluated via the piezoelectric coefficient (d_{33}) and voltage response under dynamic force. x-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed β -phase formation in P(VDF-TrFE), and layer thickness was measured due to its impact on output. These analyses identified the most effective fabrication parameters for high-performance sensors. As a result, the final sensor has a sandwiched structure less than 1 μm thick.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Firstly, in section 2, the fabrication of the piezoelectric sensors as well as the characterization methods are described. Then, in section 3, the obtained results are presented and discussed, and the most relevant ones are collected in summarizing table 4 at the end of the section. Finally, the last section outlines conclusions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fabrication of the sensor

The fabrication process of the sensors is illustrated in figure 1. The bottom electrode for the piezoelectric sensor was formed through inkjet printing (Dimatix Printer DMP-2801, Fujifilm Dimatix) a mixture of poly(3,4 ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) with 1 v% of (3-glycidyloxypropyl) trimethoxysilane (GOPS), and 6 wt% of Glycerol on polyimide (PI) substrate as depicted in figure 1(a). GOPS was added to improve the ink's chemical stability under humidity [32], and glycerol to compensate the conductivity drop caused by GOPS [33]. The substrate was first cleaned with acetone and isopropanol, then rinsed with deionized water to remove organic residuals [34]. Next, to ensure proper wetting of the ink the substrate surface was treated with oxygen plasma for 5 min (Diener Plasma). Following the inkjet printing, the electrodes were annealed at 130 °C for 1 h (figure 1(b)). The fabrication of the P(VDF-TrFE) ink started by weighing P(VDF-TrFE) powder (Piezotech FC20 from Arkema) and mixing it with a solvent. To ensure proper dissolving, the solution was stirred for 4.5 h at 60 °C for P(VDF-TrFE) in DMSO, and 4 h at room temperature for P(VDF-TrFE) in MEK.

A P(VDF-TrFE) layer was spin coated (spin coater WS650Sz-8NPP, Laurell Technologies) onto bottom electrodes at 3000 rpm for 1 min, as presented in figures 1(c) and (d). Varying compositions of P(VDF-TrFE) ink were used to form the active layer: 4 wt% and 9 wt% in MEK, and 4 wt% in DMSO. All processing parameters of the active layer are presented in table 2. After spin coating the active layer, all samples were annealed on a hot plate at 105 °C, 120 °C, or 125 °C for 10 min or 1 h. Additionally, some of the samples were annealed in an oven (125 °C, 1 h) and slowly cooled down to room temperature

(figure 1(d)). Lastly, the top electrodes were fabricated on top of the active layer by inkjet printing. Following the printing, samples were annealed at 70 °C for 30 min and then poled (figures 1(e), (f), and (g)).

2.2. Electrical characterization

2.2.1. Capacitance

The capacitance of each sample was measured (Keysight B1500A, parameters) to evaluate the electrical properties of active layer material. The attained capacitance value was also used to evaluate the thickness of the active layer according to the equation [35]:

$$d = \frac{\epsilon_r \times \epsilon_0 \times A}{C_p}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_r is approximately 10 for P(VDF-TrFE) [36], ϵ_0 is $8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{F m}^{-1}$, and A is the area of the sensor's top electrode (12 mm²). The estimated thickness was utilized to assess the required poling voltage following the capacitance measurement.

2.2.2. Poling

Intrinsically, P(VDF-TrFE) behaves like a normal dielectric material and does not exhibit high remanent polarization (P_r). To induce piezoelectricity in the material, a poling step is required, during which an electric field is applied between the top and bottom electrodes to align regions with non-zero polarization. The remanent polarization versus the applied electric field can be measured, resulting in a hysteresis loop (P-E loop) as depicted in figure 2. From the P-E loop, two essential values that characterize the material can be determined: the remanent polarization ($\pm P_r$), represented by the intersections with the polarization axis, and the coercive fields ($\pm E_C$), which correspond to the minimum voltages required to reverse the ferroelectric polarization. The E_C is found at the intersections of the P-E loop with electric field axis [37]. Typically, literature values for P_r in P(VDF-TrFE) are reported to be 6–8 $\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ [38, 39]. E_C is a material property that describes the material's ability to resist dipole switching. To change the polarization, an electric field greater than the coercive field E_C ($\approx 50 \text{MV m}^{-1}$) [40] must be applied.

From the P-E loop, the value V_C can be determined, corresponding to the voltage at the point where the electric field equals the coercive field E_C [37]. Once V_C is attained, the thickness d of the ferroelectric film (active layer) can be estimated according to:

$$E_C = \frac{V_C}{d} \iff d = \frac{V_C}{E_C}, \quad (2)$$

where E_C is the coercive field (50 MV m⁻¹), and V_C is the voltage applied at E_C .

Table 2. Fabrication parameters of P(VDF-TrFE) active layer.

Sample set	P(VDF-TrFE) ink composition			Hot plate temp. [°C]			Time on hot plate		Oven anneal 125 °C, 1 h
	4% MEK	4% DMSO	9% MEK	105	120	125	10 min	60 min	
A	•			•			•		•
B	•				•		•		•
C	•				•			•	•
D	•				•			•	•
E	•					•		•	•
F	•					•		•	•
G		•			•		•		•
H		•			•			•	•
I			•	•			•		•
J			•		•			•	•
K			•		•			•	•

2.2.3. Normal mode sensitivity

Piezoelectric materials convert mechanical strain into electrical charges [42]. The piezoelectric coefficient d_{ij} represents the amount of charge generated in the piezoelectric material in response to applied stress. As illustrated in figure 3, i and j represent the directions of the sensor's polarization and the applied stress, respectively. The subscript values 1–3 refer to the orthogonal axes, whereas values 4–6 denote rotations around their respective axes [43]. In this study, the directions of the electric field during poling

and the applied mechanical stress during sensitivity measurements are both perpendicular to the sample surface, resulting in d_{33} as the relevant piezoelectric coefficient for sensitivity measurements. Sensor sensitivity setup is presented in figure 4. To measure voltage sensitivity of the sensor, a linearly increasing dynamic force is applied on the sensor. Similarly to normal mode sensitivity measurement, the direction of the applied force during measurement is perpendicular to the sample surface. The input signal is applied with a piezometer, and the attained signal of

output voltage is measured with an oscilloscope with 30 Hz frequency.

2.3. Material characterization

The thickness of the P(VDF-TrFE) layer was measured using a stylus profilometer (Dektak XT, Bruker) at three different locations close to the center of the

sample. The surface roughness of the layer was measured simultaneously. The XRD spectra of P(VDF-TrFE) films were measured with an x-ray diffractometer (Empyrean, Panalytical).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Capacitance results

Capacitance was measured to characterize the electrical properties of the sensors and to evaluate the active layer thickness. Sample sets with no ferroelectric response were discarded. Therefore, sets A, G, H, and J were not further characterized. The average capacitance (C_p) result for each set of samples exhibiting ferroelectric behavior is presented in figure 5. It can be observed that the C_p values are relatively uniform across all samples within each sample set, with the exception of sample set B, which suggests some unevenness in the thickness of set B active layer. Evaluated thickness of the active layer was determined based on each C_p value according to equation (1). The achieved values for thicknesses are shown in table 3.

3.2. Poling results

With the estimated thickness value attained from capacitance measurement, the polarization-electric field hysteresis loop (P-E loop) measurement was performed to evaluate the sensor's ferroelectric properties. During the P-E loop measurement, a high electric field (E) is applied over the sensor while measuring the polarization (P). The saturated P-E loops for sample sets exhibiting ferroelectric behavior are presented in figure 6, and the average poling electric fields are summarized in table 4.

The highest average remanent polarization P_r of $7.9 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ was achieved with approximately $75 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ for sample set F (figure 6(d)), which exhibited very uniform P-E loops across all reference samples. This value aligns with earlier findings for P(VDF-TrFE) (P_r of $6\text{--}8 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$) [38, 39]. This suggests that the fabrication process for set F resulted in a highly uniform and thin active layer.

In sample set C (figure 6(b)), the hysteresis loops of all four reference samples are saturating around $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, with the P_r ranging between 5.6 and $8.0 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$. Variation in P_r suggests some unevenness in the active layer thickness. Despite this, sample sets C and F exhibit quite similar ferroelectric performance.

The samples of set B (figure 6(a)) display the highest variance in the electric field required for saturation of P-E loops from approximately 100 to $200 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, with average P_r of $5.6 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ (ranging between 5.0 and $6.1 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$). This suggests that while the ink deposition process during spin coating for set B failed to produce a uniform active layer, the overall piezoelectric performance remained consistent.

In both sample sets K (figure 6(e)) and E (figure 6(c)) two (out of four) functioning reference samples were achieved, which implies some uncertainty factors during the process. Samples from set K exhibit the lowest P_r values (3.3 and 4.6 $\mu C cm^{-2}$) saturating at 75 $V \mu m^{-1}$. Measured P_r for samples of set E fall between 4.7 and 6.1 $\mu C cm^{-2}$.

The coercive field E_C measures the order of magnitude of the field that must be applied to a material to reverse its polarization. For P(VDF-TrFE), a theoretical value for coercive field is about 50 $V \mu m^{-1}$ [29]. In figure 7, the results for coercive field of P(VDF-TrFE) indicate lower values, which were attained as

a ratio of the coercive voltage V_C and thickness of the active layer measured with Dektak profilometer.

The coercive field V_C was additionally utilized to estimate the active layer thickness according to equation (2). Results for the attained values are presented in table 3 among the other thickness characterizations.

One objective of this study was to evaluate whether the choice of casting solvent influences ferroelectric performance of the P(VDF-TrFE) layer. Two solvents were selected for comparison: DMSO, a polar aprotic solvent with high water miscibility, and MEK, a less polar aprotic solvent with limited water

Figure 7. Average coercive field of each sample set. Maximum and minimum values of each sample set are presented as error bars.

(a) Sample from set G with DMSO as the casting solvent. (b) Sample from set C with MEK as the casting solvent.

Figure 8. Optical microscope images of P(VDF-TrFE) layer comparing two solvents, DMSO and MEK. Magnification: 1,75 x.

solubility [44]. According to [29], VIPS is more likely to occur in P(VDF-TrFE) films cast from solvents that are more miscible with water.

Indeed, after the spin coating it was visually observed that the samples with DMSO ink were clearly non-uniform and during P-E measurements showed no ferroelectricity. A closer look with an optical microscope reveals that the P(VDF-TrFE) layer cast in DMSO exhibits gaps in the active layer whereas the layer cast in MEK is completely uniform, as presented in figure 8.

3.3. Active layer thickness characterization

The thickness of the active layer was characterized by three different methods: calculated from the capacitance value C_p , calculated from coercive voltage V_C , and by direct measurement with a profilometer. In addition, the surface roughness of the active layer was measured for one sample from each set. The obtained values are shown in table 3.

It can be observed that the thickness values from different measurement methods are well aligned for sample sets C and F, for which the maximum differences are 65 nm and 83 nm, respectively. This consistency supports the conclusion that the fabrication process for sample sets C and F results in a

uniform and smooth active layer. Interestingly, the roughness in sample set C is the highest (2.8%), still remaining low compared with values reported in the literature [45].

For sample set K, the thickness of the piezoelectric film is the highest. This is likely due to the highest concentration of P(VDF-TrFE) in spin coated ink (9 wt% P(VDF-TrFE) in MEK).

3.4. XRD results

P(VDF-TrFE) has lamellar crystals which orientate either edge-on or face-on. The edge-on structure, where the lamellae point out of plane, exhibits strong ferroelectricity, whereas the face-on (in-plane lamellar) structure shows weaker ferroelectric response. To achieve the edge-on orientation, the P(VDF-TrFE) crystallization temperature must be above the Curie temperature T_c but below the melting temperature T_m . Crystallization outside the temperature window results in the face-on orientation. In XRD diffraction analysis, the needle-like edge-on structure produces a diffraction peak at 20° [46]. The crystallinity of the fabricated samples was studied using XRD, with the patterns shown in figure 9. The XRD data show peaks at 18.8° and 26.4° for the PI substrate. For the samples with a PI/P(VDF-TrFE) structure, peaks

Table 3. Thickness values of P(VDF-TrFE) layer determined by different methods and roughness measurements.

Sample set	Thickness from capacitance C_p (nm)	Thickness from coercive voltage V_c (nm), ($E_c = 50 \text{ MV m}^{-1}$)	Thickness from Dektak profilometer (nm)	Roughness (nm) (percentage of thickness)
B	409	470	641	4.1 (0.6%)
C	331	266	271	7.5 (2.8%)
E	3766	343	459	7.7 (1.7%)
F	416	320	391	2.6 (0.7%)
K	1540	1188	1470	13.7 (0.9%)

Figure 10. Average piezoelectric coefficients of sample sets with minimum and maximum values as error bars.

appear at 20.6° and 26.4° , where the first peak corresponds to the β -phase peak of P(VDF-TrFE) and the second from the PI substrate. While the proximity of the 18.8° PI peak was considered, the 20.6° peak is distinct and consistently appears only in samples containing P(VDF-TrFE), supporting its attribution to the β phase. This observation is consistent with the literature [47] and further confirms the structural characteristics of the polymer layer. These results suggest that the crystallization conditions significantly impact the ferroelectric properties of P(VDF-TrFE) and that the XRD analysis effectively reveals the structural orientation of the material.

3.5. Sensor sensitivity (d_{33}) results

To characterize the piezoelectric sensitivity of the sensors, the pressure sensing properties were measured in normal mode (d_{33}) by applying a force perpendicular to substrate surface. The average measured piezoelectric sensitivities are presented in figure 10, with error bars indicating the minimum and maximum. On average, the sensitivities are lower than values typically reported in the literature (19 pC N^{-1} [48], 25 pC N^{-1} [49], 28 pC N^{-1} [50]). This might be due to the quite small size (12 mm^2) of top electrode area which posed challenges while doing the measurement. In addition, the flexible substrate results in uneven deformation during characterization. Surprisingly, the sensitivity values for

sample set C remain low, even though both sets C and F exhibit good ferroelectric hysteresis loops in P-E measurements. Some sets have quite large variation in measured sensitivity values. Similarly to low values on average, the inconsistency most likely results from flexible substrate and small sample size.

3.6. Voltage sensitivity results

To evaluate sensor sensitivity, the output voltage of a sample exhibiting high ferroelectric behavior from sample set F was measured with digital storage oscilloscope. The scale of dynamic force was varied from 0.05 N to 0.50 N using 30 Hz frequency. The measurement set up as well as the output voltage plotted as function of the applied force are presented in figures 11(a) and (b), respectively.

The linear increase of the output voltage as a function of the applied force indicates the sensor's capability to function as a pressure sensor [51]. For a tactile sensor in robotic skin, a force sensitivity range of $\approx 0.01 - 10 \text{ N}$ is desirable [52]. The piezoelectric sensor presented in this work therefore covers the lowest part of the sensitivity range, although linearity of the curve suggests the possibility of extending the range.

Figure 11. Voltage sensitivity measurement.

Table 4. Summary of results.

Sample set	Thickness (nm) from Cp / Vc / profilometer	Roughness (nm) (percentage of profilometer thickness)	Poling electric field (V μm ⁻¹)	Piezoelectric coefficient d ₃₃ (pC N ⁻¹)	Remanent polarization P _r (μC cm ⁻²)	Coercive voltage V _c
B	409 / 470 / 641	4.1 (0.6%)	133	10.9	5.6	23.5
C	331 / 266 / 271	7.5 (2.8%)	89	12.6	7.1	13.3
E	3766 / 343 / 459	7.7 (1.7%)	12	9.5	5.4	17.2
F	416 / 320 / 391	2.6 (0.7%)	73	12.4	7.9	16.5
K	1540 / 1188 / 1470	13.7 (0.7%)	77	6.7	4.0	67.5

3.7. Summarizing table of results

In table 4, the findings presented in the results section are summarized. In table 5, fabrication parameters as well as the main characteristics of ferroelectricity for each sample set are presented. Samples with short circuits or with very low yield (less than 25%) were discarded as non-functional. P(VDF-TrFE) thin films cast in DMSO (sample sets G and H) were

found to produce non-uniform layers. In addition, with samples annealed in 105 °C (sample sets A and I) or in 120 °C without the oven annealing step (sample sets D and J), no ferroelectric behavior was detected. Fabrication parameters for sets C and F were found to result in very similar performance despite set F samples lacking the oven annealing.

Table 5. Active layer fabrication parameters with resulting remanent polarization and sensor sensitivities.

Sample set	P(VDF-TrFE) ink composition			Hot plate temp.(°C)			Time on hot plate		Oven anneal:	Remanent polarization P_r ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$)	Sensor sensitivity d_{33} (pC N ⁻¹)
	4% MEK	4% DMSO	9% MEK	105	120	125	10 min	60 min	125 °C, 1 h		
A	•			•			•		•		
B	•				•		•		•	5.6	10.9
C	•				•			•	•	7.1	12.6
D	•				•			•	•		
E	•					•		•	•	5.4	9.5
F	•					•		•	•	7.9	12.4
G		•			•		•		•		
H		•			•			•	•		
I			•	•			•		•		
J			•		•			•	•		
K			•		•			•	•	4.0	6.7

4. Conclusions

Flexible and conformable materials are essential for the development of electronics suitable for applications in healthcare, wearables, and robotics. However, these materials pose unique challenges for fabrication methods, as traditional approaches for rigid electronics are not fully compatible. To address these challenges and ensure the process is cost-effective and energy-efficient, it is necessary to use low processing temperatures while minimizing material waste.

In this study, we demonstrate the fabrication of an all-solution-based piezoelectric sensor, with inkjet-printed PEDOT:PSS used as electrodes and spin-coated P(VDF-TrFE) as the active layer. To evaluate solvent effects, two casting solvents with different hygroscopic properties—DMSO and MEK—were assessed for their impact on the ferroelectric properties of P(VDF-TrFE). P(VDF-TrFE) dissolved in DMSO failed to produce uniform thin films, whereas P(VDF-TrFE) cast in MEK resulted in smooth and uniform layer. Furthermore, various annealing conditions for the piezoelectric layer were investigated. As a result, this study identifies two alternative fabrication routes that lead to sensors with high piezoelectric performance: first, samples with spin coated active layer annealed on a hot plate at 120 °C, followed by oven annealing at 125 °C and slow cooling to room temperature (sample set C). Second, samples with spin coated active layer annealed on a hot plate at 125 °C for 1 h (sample set F). In both situations, 4 wt% P(VDF-TrFE) in MEK was used for spin coating (3000 rpm, 1 min).

Regarding the piezoelectric performance, the highest remanent polarization (P_r) observed from PE-measurements was $7.9 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ in sample set F, and the average piezoelectric coefficient of sample set C was 12.6 pC N^{-1} . The voltage sensitivity of one of the top-performing samples showed linear increase from 0 N to 0.5 N, generating a voltage up to 0.086 mV. Thus, two efficient and sustainable fabrication methods for piezoelectric sensors have been demonstrated.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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